

Recommended citation: Riedel, U., Jakobtorweihen, S., & Bornhöft, S. (2019). Curricular network analysis. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 909-916). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656591.

Curricular Network Analysis

U. Riedel

Center for Teaching and Learning, Hamburg University of Technology
Hamburg, Germany
uta.riedel@tuhh.de

S. Jakobtorweihen

Institute of Thermal Separation Processes, Hamburg University of Technology
Hamburg, Germany

S. Bornhöft

Center for Teaching and Learning, Hamburg University of Technology
Hamburg, Germany

Conference Key Areas: New Complexity Quest in Engineering Sciences, Strong demand for democratic involvement in educational

Keywords: curriculum analysis, curriculum development, network visualisation, chemical engineering

ABSTRACT

Academics usually have a good overview of their discipline which allows them to rapidly integrate new knowledge into a general context. Students often lack this overview and need to develop an own picture of their discipline and the connections between different subjects and courses.

For an analysis of the bachelor program in chemical engineering at the Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), lecturers wanted to know how their students perceive the cross-links between different lectures.

Therefore, a method was developed to analyse students' perceptions of the links between lectures, called curricular network analysis. Attending a lecture, students take structured notes on topics, formulas or facts if they either recognise them as parts of other lectures or if the lecturer points out the connections. All notes are added to a database which is subsequently analysed with regard to the connecting topics and the frequency of their occurrence. Graphical illustrations of the results give a vivid impression of connections between single lectures and of the network of contents that characterise the whole study program.

The visualisation can rapidly spark a discussion between lecturers because it allows them to compare their own concepts with the perceptions of the students. Since it facilitates identifying redundant repetitions and missing references between courses, it enables a learner-orientated restructuring of the study program.

This paper describes the method in detail, presents results of an investigation with a group of students and shows how the obtained data were used for restructuring the bachelor program in (bio-)chemical engineering at TUHH.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Curriculum Development

When developing curricula, different points must be taken care of, for example the following criteria:

- successive building of a network of knowledge,
- increasing difficulty of scientific methods, e.g. used in the laboratories,
- increasing level of independency of students work, and
- variability of exams.

Usually lecturers create a curriculum that fits as many criteria as possible in order to develop a concept that allows students to learn in the best way possible and finally meet the goals of the study program, usually a university degree [1, 2].

Concerning the first factor mentioned above, the building of a network of knowledge, a number of graphical methods exist that depict the interdependency of the different topics within a study program, either on course level or on a level linking contents. They usually visualise the intended knowledge network but do not take into account students' perceptions. For example in [3], first-year students derive their study map based on the study handbook and given content-related interconnections, which is useful to get an overview of the overall program right at the start.

1.2 Students' Perceptions

Lecturers of our technical university wanted to know whether their effort in the curriculum development was successful and whether they met their intended objectives of creating a course that builds a successive knowledge network. The questions asked were: How well do students perceive the cross-linking between the study topics? Do they recognise the links we intended them to see? To answer these questions, a method was developed to analyse the students' perceptions of the interconnection of content details within a study program.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Approach

Right from the beginning, our aim was the primarily *automatic* generation of a graph or concept map which would show the interdependent structure of the collected data. To achieve this, we needed a data structure allowing for automatic processing. Having sorted this out, we successively developed the data collection and analysis methodology.

2.2 Data collection

Students from different semesters of a study program take notes during their lectures as soon as they detect a fact which they remember from a previous course. In each course they attend, they note the name of the course, the course format (i.e., lecture, exercise, laboratory work) and the fact itself they recognise (i.e., a formula, a natural law, a physical property, a method etc.). They also write down whether they

themselves recognised this fact or whether the lecturer made a corresponding remark, and they additionally mark this entry if there was a repetition of a whole topic rather than a brief mentioning of fact. For follow-ups, they also note their names and the semester week. The data is then verified and collected in a data table.

2.3 Data Processing

Since students are free to use their own words while making notes, they might use different terms for the same topic. Those similarities are best recognisable by an expert in the courses and have to be matched by hand. Thus, to process the collected data, the first step is to match the facts that are named differently by different students, but refer to the same concepts.

Following this, true duplications are automatically eliminated. Only one incident per fact and lecture remains. The aim is to avoid a duplication of entries due to a larger number of students attending the same lecture.

We also noticed that it is useful to group different courses when students did not exactly remember in which previous lecture they learned about the facts. For example, courses in mathematics from the first three semesters (“Mathematics I”, “Mathematics II” and “Mathematics III”) were grouped to “Mathematics”.

2.4 Data Analysis

Different questions can now be answered by an automated analysis: How many references and which references were found between two courses? Did the students recognize them by themselves or did the lecturer mention them? With regard to this, what is the lecturers share? Or with regard to a single course: To which other courses and to how many other courses do references exist? Which course repeats most topics? How many references between courses exist overall in the whole study program?

2.5 Graphical Visualisation

The obtained data from the database can be plotted in different graphs for ease of recognition of the results.

In *Fig. 1*, an exemplary overall graph for an entire study program is given. Courses are shown in ovals, the identified connection between courses are shown by lines. The width of the lines corresponds to the number of connections between two courses. Hence, wide lines mean that a large number of references between courses were found and slim lines indicate a smaller number of references. The percentage of links identified by students is depicted in black, the percentage of links mentioned by lecturers is depicted in orange.

In *Fig. 2*, an exemplary graph for a single course - shown in red - is given. Courses are shown in ovals. The recognized references are listed in boxes attached to the connections between the courses. Boxes with grey background show comprehensive repetitions whereas orange borders mark the connections mentioned by lecturers.

Fig. 1: Graphical visualisation of the course interconnections within a study program. Courses are represented by blue ellipsoids. Wide lines correspond to large numbers of references between courses, slim lines to small numbers. The coloration of the lines indicates the percentage of links found by students (black) or mentioned by lecturers (orange), respectively.

Fig. 2: Section of the graphical visualisation of the connections and referential topics between a single course (in red) and other courses in the study program. Grey boxes mark topics that were thoroughly repeated in the lecture and orange borders mark references to other courses mentioned by the lecturer. For better understanding, one detail showing links between two courses is enlarged.

2.6 Data Formats and Software Tools

The collected data were saved to an *Excel* file. The data sets were subsequently analysed by a *Python* script which produced data for network analysis and network visualisation. For the latter the open source graph visualisation software *GraphViz* [4] was used, therefore the *Python* script created a file in DOT format.

3 APPLICATION

3.1 Investigated courses

The curricular network analysis was applied to two bachelor programs that have a number of courses in common - the bachelor of chemical engineering and the bachelor of biochemical engineering.

3.2 Participating students

The data collection took place during the two semesters of the study year 2017/18. In the winter semester, courses of the third and fifth semester of both bachelor programs were investigated and in the summer semester, courses of the fourth and sixth semester. Connections between the basic courses within the first semester and from the second semester to courses of the first and second semester were of no higher interest and therefore omitted. It was made sure that at least two students were attending each course. Overall, about 10 students participated in the data collection.

3.3 Setup and practical aspects

Within the first weeks students tested two different methods to take notes. For one method students were asked to tick references in a prepared sheet listing all references possible and to write down additionally found references into the list. For the other method students rather took free graphical notes in the format similar to a concept map [5]. After three weeks of trial, we discussed the methods and finally omitted the prepared lists. Students took free notes either in an empty sheet or in a personal concept map. Each week, students handed in their notes which were then verified and transferred to a data table. *Fig. 3* shows an exemplary section of the resulting table.

My course			Link found to			Semester Week
Course	Topic	For-mat*	Course	Mentioned by Lecturer	Repetition	
Str	Reynolds number	Lec	PC		x	2
Str	Basic equation of hydrostatics	Exe	Ph			4
T3	Enthalpy	Lec	T1	x		2
T3	Taylor expansion	Exe	M1			5
GBVT	Viscosity	Lec	Str			9
GBVT	Stirrers	Lec	Str	x		9
Inf	Energy flow	Lec	T1			1
PAT	Thermal capacity flow		TGO			3
PAT	Boiling point, melting point		KA	x		4
PF	Continuous, disperse phase	Lec	TGO			1
PF	Gibbs free energy	Lec	CRT			1
TGO	Rotameter	Lab	MT			2
CRT	Laminar, turbulent flow	Lab	Str			7

Fig. 3: Data table with notes of courses (abbreviations are used) and referential topics between courses. (Lec: lectures, Exe: exercises, Lab: laboratory work)*

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Collected Data

Overall, 1616 references between 30 courses were identified which were plotted in full graphs for the overall study program and in individual graphs for each course (see *Fig. 1* and *Fig. 2*). The highest number of reference topics between two courses was 373. Courses with a high affinity of topics and courses with rather low affinity can easily be identified from the graphs. It can easily be seen where a lecturer refers quite often to another course or, where a lecturer decided to often repeat contents of other courses.

4.2 Discussion of the qualitative and quantitative analysis

Qualitative analysis involves *finding* the references between courses. Even though the students participating in the study showed a high commitment, we were aware that the findings might not be complete. Due to the rather small sample size (about two students in each course) and the free choice of references, there will undoubtedly be references that were not found. However, as inspection of the data by the experts showed, the main topics were covered.

Quantitative analysis involves *counting the number of* references between courses. Equally due to the individual choice of topics by the students, the references range from physical properties to natural laws and therefore are not easily comparable. When discussing the results of the analysis this must be taken into account. It is therefore not feasible to use the data to compare the number of references between courses or establish a “ranking”. However, the numbers can be used as indicators and initiate a closer look at the lists of references.

4.3 Interpretation of results

The results visible in the graphs spark a number of questions and can be discussed in different ways.

Strong connections between courses with a large number of references (shown as wide lines in *Fig. 1*) indicate large overlaps, but are there (too) many redundancies and could they possibly be removed in favour of other topics?

Frequent occurrences of repetitions can lead to the question whether all of them are required, e.g. for a consolidation of difficult learning matters or to reintroduce a topic after a longer break. It could also open space for thinking about new themes.

Weak connections between courses with a low number of references (shown as slim lines in *Fig. 1*) can indicate that this course is a special course with unique features. Here it could possibly be helpful to think about introducing examples to strengthen the interconnection with other courses.

Based on the analysis, the content connections between two courses can be discussed: Are the results consistent with the expectations of lecturers? Do students detect all relevant references, or are references missing? Those discussions can lead to further development of courses or setting of priorities within the curriculum.

Are courses given by lecturers of other faculties well embedded within the program?
Are there possible ways to enhance their integration?

As can be seen, the curricular network analysis is not necessarily a tool that yields defined numbers and results, but - largely due to the visualisation - can be used as a trigger for discussion about a study program.

4.4 Use of the results for further development of the curriculum

At our university, the results of the analysis were presented at a large meeting of all faculty lecturers. Posters with network graphs were on display and were vividly discussed. A subsequent meeting between several lecturers and students was initiated to overcome some of the challenges of the curriculum. As a result, a number of courses were shifted between semesters, and contents of courses were adapted.

For the participating students, the study also had a strong effect. During the study they continuously recommended improvements of the method. And to see the final results of their work made them feel proud about their contributions and led to understanding and discussions about the cross-links within their study program.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The results of the curricular network analysis are a very helpful source for a reflection about a study program. The graphical visualisations yield intriguing pictures engineers cannot withstand to discuss. The method also involves students directly and fosters their participation in the process of curriculum development.

Since the resulting data need interpretation, the method should at best be embedded into a larger project of developing a study program.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fung, D., A Connected Curriculum for Higher Education (2017), USL Press, London
- [2] Brinker, T, Tremp, P. (eds.) (2012), Einführung in die Studiengangentwicklung, W. Bertelsmann Verlag, Bielefeld
- [3] Beer, S., Ladwig, D. H., Knedel, F., Fachlandkarten: Supporting Students' Self-Organisation and Collaborative Learning *in* Jansen-Schulz, B., Tantau, T. (eds.) (2018), Excellent Teaching. Principles, Structures and Requirements, wbv Publication, Bielefeld, pp. 225-235.
- [4] Graphviz - Graph Visualization Software, www.graphviz.org (accessed 21th June 2019)
- [5] Gehl, D. (2013), Vom Betrachten zum Verstehen. Die Diagnose von Rezeptionsprozessen und Wissensveränderungen bei multimodalen Printclustern, Springer VS, Wiesbaden